

Comparison of GC-NCI-MS, GC-ICP-MS and GC-EI-MS/MS for the determination of PBDEs in water samples according to the Water Framework Directive (WFD)

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Abstract

The Water Framework Directive (WFD) includes some polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs) in the list of priority substances that must be measured in surface waters at very low concentration levels. The typical approaches applied to the determination of PBDEs in environmental samples might not be suitable to meet the demanding requirements of the WFD.

In this work, the instrumental capabilities of the MS techniques most frequently used in the determination of PBDEs (GC-NCI-MS, GC-EI-MS/MS) are evaluated in comparison with the highly sensitive GC-ICP-MS for the reliable determination of PBDEs according to the WFD. Three analytical methods based on the liquid-liquid extraction of water samples and measurement of the extracts by GC-NCI-MS, GC-EI-MS/MS or GC-ICP-MS are described. The priority PBDEs were quantified in different types of water samples by means of Isotope Dilution Mass Spectrometry (IDMS) using ^{81}Br -labelled or ^{13}C -labelled PBDEs spikes, depending on the selected ionization source. The three proposed methodologies were able to meet the requirements of the European legislation in terms of LOQs and expanded uncertainties. The determination method using ^{81}Br -labelled PBDEs and GC-ICP-MS showed the highest sensitivity and the lowest instrumental limits of detection and expanded uncertainties.

Keywords

Surface water, Isotope Dilution Mass Spectrometry (IDMS), ^{81}Br -labelled standards, priority substances, hetero element specific detection

Introduction

The current European legislation requires the monitoring of the so-called priority substances in surface waters to control and protect their chemical quality status [1]. Polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs) have been included in the list of priority substances and identified as priority hazardous substances [2] as they are known to endanger human health and harm the environment [3]. PBDEs are a group of organic compounds that have been widely used as flame retardants in different types of polymeric materials. Despite the fact that their production has been phased out for years [4] they are still present in many old electronic devices, household furnishing and appliances that are currently still in use. PBDEs are additive flame retardants [5, 6] so they are not chemically (covalently) bound to the base material containing them. Therefore, they can easily release from the materials to which they are added into the environment and, due to their physicochemical properties, e.g. PBDEs are semivolatile, resistant to degradation and highly lipophilic [3], they reach all relevant environmental compartments [5]. Their persistence and ability to bioaccumulate and biomagnify [7] together with the potential adverse effects of PBDEs in living organisms [8], especially the lower brominated congeners present in the c-pentaBDE (pentabrominated diphenyl ether commercial mixture) and c-octaBDE (octabrominated diphenyl ether commercial mixture) [9], has led to their final classification as Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) according to the Stockholm Convention and their regulation by different institutions.

On a European level, according to the provisions and objectives of the Water Framework Directive (WFD) [1], Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) have been set for the six major congeners of the c-pentaBDE commercial product (28, 47, 99, 100, 153 and 154). The EQS values (annual average) were set at $0.0005 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and $0.0002 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ respectively, for inland (rivers and lakes) and other surface waters (transitional, coastal and territorial waters) [10]. However, these values have been reviewed and new maximum allowable concentration values have been set for the sum of the six priority congeners in inland ($0.14 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), other surface waters ($0.014 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) and biota ($0.0085 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) with effect from 22 December 2015 [11]. In addition, the Directive 2009/90/EC states that analytical methods that are to be applied for the determination of the priority substances named in the WFD must meet certain minimum performance criteria. The expanded uncertainties must be lower than 50% at the EQS level ($k=2$) and the limits of quantification (LOQs) must be lower than 30% of the EQS value [12]. Taking into account the demanding requirements specified by the current legislation it is clear that highly accurate and sensitive analytical methods are required for the reliable determination of PBDEs in water samples at such a low concentration levels [13]. On the other hand, as the new EQS set for PBDEs in surface water [11] are higher than they were before, achieving the minimum performance criteria requirements for analytical methods to be applied to their determination will be easier once the new Directive takes effect. So, methods

developed to comply with the current legislation should presumably comply with the new regulation, providing even more reliable measurements.

Most of the published works deals with the determination of PBDEs in biota, sediments and soils because these very hydrophobic substances will show higher affinity for these matrices than water [14]. The analytical methods used for the determination of PBDEs usually include the extraction of the samples and clean-up of the extracts followed by the separation of the different congeners, typically by Gas Chromatography (GC), and detection using typical organic Mass Spectrometric (MS) techniques. However, the determination of PBDEs in water samples is more challenging, as much lower concentrations are expected, and only few published works deal with the determination of PBDEs in water samples at the concentration levels set in the WFD [15–18]. The proposed analytical methods combine sample preparation procedures with high enrichment factors and the instrumental systems with the lowest limits of detection (LODs). Liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) [15, 17, 18] or solid phase extraction (SPE) [16] followed by the pre-concentration of the extracts to a few microliters have been chosen in most of the literature. Some attempts to minimise the amount of solvents used for the extraction of PBDEs have been carried out in the last years but unfortunately they have not yet been adapted to the requirements of the WFD [19, 20]. The detection of PBDEs in environmental samples has been mainly carried out by MS as it is considered the most suitable instrumental technique [19]. GC coupled to high resolution instruments (HRMS) offers the best selectivity and the lowest LODs for the determination of PBDEs, making possible to achieve the LOQs required by the WFD [16]. However, low resolution instruments (LRMS) are usually preferred, as they are cheaper and easier to operate than HRMS [21]. The Negative Chemical Ionisation source (NCI) has been frequently selected when working with LR instruments as provides good selectivity and much lower LOD than the Electron Ionisation (EI) for PBDEs [21, 22]. The GC-NCI-MS technique has been applied to the determination of PBDEs in water samples showing very low LODs [15, 23] and expanded uncertainties below 50% as set in the WFD [15]. In the last years GC-EI-MS/MS has been also applied to the determination of PBDEs in water samples, showing good instrumental capabilities in terms of selectivity and improved limits of detection in comparison with single quadrupole instruments, due to the low backgrounds obtained by removing most of the matrix interferences when working in the selected reaction monitoring mode (SRM) [24, 25]. Recently, ICP-MS has been also considered as GC detector for the determination of PBDEs, as despite being typically used for elemental inorganic analysis, it also offers the possibility to measure PBDEs by monitoring the signal of bromine showing high sensitivity and selectivity [19]. Some analytical methods based on ICP-MS detection of PBDEs have been published and demonstrated to meet all the requirements set in the WFD [17, 18].

According to the literature, ICP-MS seems to be the most appropriate detection technique for the reliable determination of PBDEs in water samples at the EQS concentration level. However, the

potential offered by other MS techniques has not been fully evaluated for this purpose. The instrumental capabilities of the different MS techniques cannot be easily compared from the published analytical methods, as different sample preparation procedures with different enrichment factors are usually applied, and the relevant figures of merit (LOQs and expanded uncertainties) are not always provided or calculated following the same procedures.

The aim of this work is to compare the instrumental capabilities of different MS techniques for reliable determination of PBDEs at low concentrations in natural water samples. Three analytical methods based on the liquid-liquid extraction of the samples and measurement of the extracts by GC-NCI-MS, GC-EI-MS/MS or GC-ICP-MS respectively are described. The priority PBDEs are quantified in different types of water samples by Isotope Dilution Mass Spectrometry (IDMS) using ^{81}Br -labelled or ^{13}C -labelled PBDEs spikes as species specific standards, depending on the selected ionization source. The results obtained by different proposed methods are compared and discussed.

Experimental

Chemicals and standards

A standard solution (EPA method 1614 native PAR stock solution) containing a mixture of 8 native PBDEs (BDE 28, BDE 47, BDE 99, BDE 100, BDE 153, BDE 154, BDE 183 and BDE 209) in nonane was obtained from Cambridge Isotope Laboratories Inc. (CIL, Andover, MA, USA). Diluted solutions of this standard were used to fortify the river water sample matrix and to prepare the calibration curve for the quantification of PBDEs by Isotope Dilution Mass Spectrometry (IDMS).

Individual $^{13}\text{C}_{12}$ labelled PBDEs standard solutions for the six priority congeners (BDE 28, BDE 47, BDE 99, BDE 100, BDE 153 and BDE 154, 99% isotopic purity, $50\ \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in nonane), obtained from CIL (Andover, MA, USA), were used to spike the samples and the standard solutions used to prepare the calibration curve in all the organic IDMS experiments.

Individual ^{81}Br enriched PBDEs for the six priority congeners (BDE 28, BDE 47, BDE 99, BDE 100, BDE 153 and BDE 154), obtained from ISC Science (Oviedo, Spain), were used to spike the water samples for the quantification of PBDEs by elemental IDMS. The spikes were fully characterised in concentration and isotopic composition before use by reverse IDMS using a certified reference material with NIST traceable concentrations (*SRM 2257 PBDE congeners in 2,2,4-Trimethylpentane* [26]).

A model SPM material (suspended particulate matter) containing known amounts of PBDEs was provided by the Institute for Reference Materials and Measurements (IRMM, Geel, Belgium) [27]. The model SPM was used to spike mineral water samples to mimic surface water.

All solvents used in this work were specified for organic trace analysis. Isooctane (Suprasolv® from Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) was used to prepare standard calibration solutions (organic IDMS) and as keeper for all the sample extracts. 2-propanol (Suprasolv® from Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) was used to prepare diluted solutions of the mixtures of PBDEs, unlabelled (EPA method 1614 native PAR stock solution) for the fortification of the river water samples and ¹³C- or ⁸¹Br-labelled to spike the samples for IDMS quantification. Hexane (Unisolv® from Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) and dichloromethane (Picograde® from LGC Promochem, Wesel, Germany) were used to extract the water samples. Standard working solutions and water sample extracts were stored in the dark at 4 °C until their use or analysis.

All the reusable glassware (amber bottles, separatory funnels and pre-concentration tubes) was cleaned with detergent in a laboratory glassware dish washer, rinsed with ultrapure water and baked for 10 h at 250 °C. Hexane and acetone (both Picograde® from LGC Promochem, Wesel, Germany) were used to rinse all the glassware after and before use. Disposable glassware was also rinsed with hexane and acetone and baked prior to use.

Helium 5.0 was used as carrier gas in all GC separations and as collision gas inside the octopole reaction system for GC-ICP-MS analysis. Nitrogen 5.0 was also used as an additional plasma gas for sensitivity enhancement in GC-ICP-MS measurements. Argon 5.0 was used as plasma gas and carrier gas for the GC interface. Methane 5.5 was used as reagent gas in the Chemical Ionisation source used in GC-NCI-MS analysis. A mixture of nitrogen 5.0 and helium 5.0 (quench gas) was used to pressurize the collision cell of the GC-EI-MS/MS. Helium, nitrogen and argon were obtained from Messer Griesheim (Messer Griesheim, Krefeld, Germany) and methane was obtained from Alphasgaz -Air Liquide (Düsseldorf, Germany).

Instrumentation

An Agilent 6890 gas chromatography system (Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany) equipped with an Agilent 7683 series auto-sampler was coupled to an Agilent 7700cs ICP-MS (Agilent Technologies, Tokyo, Japan). An Agilent GC-ICP-MS interface which features a temperature controlled Silcosteel® transfer line as well as a heated stainless steel injector tip was used for the hyphenation of GC and ICP-MS (Agilent Technologies, Tokyo, Japan) [28]. The GC was also equipped with an additional 3 way gas-flow controller which allows the precise mixing of different gases to the ICP-MS controlled carrier-gas.

A GC model 6890N (Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany) equipped with a MSD model 5975B (Agilent Technologies, Tokyo, Japan) and a 7683B auto-sampler was operated in the NCI mode using methane as reagent gas in the ionisation source.

A 7000B triple quadrupole GCMS system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) coupled with a GC model 7890B (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) and equipped with a Agilent 7683B (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) autosampler was operated in the EI ionisation mode

The three assayed GCMS instrumental systems were equipped with a cool on column (COC) injection port. A DB5MS capillary column 0.25 mm I.D., 0.10 µm film thickness and 15 m length (J&W Scientific, Folsom, CA, USA) was used in all cases.

Samples

Dark glass bottled natural still mineral water (from Fürst Bismark source, Aumühle, Germany) was bought in a local supermarket and was used to prepare the water samples containing model SPM and the blank samples. The SPM containing water samples were prepared by spiking the mineral water samples with a slurry containing the model SPM to achieve concentration levels between 0.03-4.48 ng L⁻¹ in the water sample depending on the priority congener [27].

River water samples were collected from the River Elbe. The fortified river water samples were obtained by spiking the River Elbe water samples with a mixture of native PBDEs. Diluted solutions of the standard mixture were prepared to achieve final concentration levels around half of the EQS value for each priority PBDE in the river water sample. The fortified samples were mechanically shaken for 20 min and then stored in the dark (4 °C, 48 h) before analysis to allow the full equilibration of the sample.

The spiking solution and the slurry used for the fortification of the mineral and river water samples were prepared and added to the samples gravimetrically using an analytical balance (AT261 Delta Range from Mettler-Toledo, Greifensee, Switzerland).

Sample preparation

All the labelled spikes (⁸¹Br and ¹³C) were prepared and added to the samples gravimetrically using an analytical balance (AT261 Delta Range from Mettler-Toledo, Greifensee, Switzerland).

The water samples were placed into 1 L amber glass bottles and spiked with a mixture of the six ⁸¹Br (for GC-ICP-MS and GC-NCI-MS measurements) or ¹³C (for GC-EI-MSMS measurements) enriched PBDEs in isopropanol. After equilibration (48 h) the samples were extracted three times with a mixture of hexane and dichloromethane (1:1). The extracts were pre-concentrated, first by rotary evaporation and afterwards under a nitrogen flow using a heated gas flow laboratory evaporator (Flowtherm Optocontrol from Barkey, Leopoldshoehe, Germany), to get a final volume

around 50 - 75 μL . Finally the extracts were injected into the appropriate measurement system. A mineral water sample was run in parallel to each set of samples to control the procedural blanks.

Results and discussion

Optimisation of the instrumental settings

The chromatographic conditions selected in this work were identical for the three evaluated MS instruments to ensure the comparability of the different instrumental systems. A cold on column (COC) injection port was used in combination with a short, non-polar column with a thin stationary phase in order to minimise the potential thermal degradation and discrimination effects and to improve the precision in the determination of PBDEs, in comparison to the frequently used split/splitless injector [29]. The experimental working conditions were selected to achieve a baseline separation of the six priority congeners [18]. Details on the chromatographic working conditions are summarized in Table S1.

The three detection techniques considered in this work, GC-ICP-MS, GC-NCI-MS and GC-EI-MS/MS, were selected for their high selectivity and sensitivity for the detection of PBDEs. Moreover, all of them allow the development of IDMS procedures allowing the accurate quantification of PBDEs. These techniques can be commonly found in typical environmental laboratories, as they are more affordable and easier to operate than the HRMS instruments and so, they have been demonstrated to be a good alternative to HRMS, when working under optimized conditions [18, 30]. More details regarding the selected measurement techniques and the used optimal working conditions can be found in the electronic supplementary material.

Comparison of the instrumental capabilities of the evaluated MS techniques

The instrumental capabilities of the different MS techniques were evaluated in terms of sensitivity, precision and instrumental limits of detection. These parameters were obtained by injecting standard solutions containing a mixture of the target PBDEs at different concentration levels (0, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 1, 5, and 10 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$).

Sensitivity

The different techniques were first compared in terms of sensitivity, as a higher sensitivity usually provides a better precision in the measurements and lower limits of detection. For the comparison the sensitivity was expressed in terms of the slope of the calibration curve obtained by injecting the different standard solutions. For the two sources generating bromine ions (ICP and NCI) the sensitivity of both bromine isotopes ($m/z = 79$ and 81) was evaluated, as they both will need to be measured for elemental IDMS quantification. For the EI source, the sensitivity was evaluated only for the MS/MS transition selected as optimal for the quantification. The obtained results are shown

in Table 1. As can be observed the GC-ICP-MS provided the highest sensitivity for the six priority congeners and it was in the same range in all cases. The GC-NCI-MS showed lower sensitivities and they were in the same range for all the congeners as well. Finally, the GC-EI-MS/MS showed overall lower sensitivities than GC-ICP-MS and GC-NCI-MS especially for the higher brominated congeners, being for the hexabrominated PBDEs (153 and 154) up to 10 and 5 times lower respectively. The results are in agreement with the behaviour described in the literature for the three studied ionisation sources [20, 31].

Precision

A second parameter to be considered for the comparison of the instrumental capabilities of the proposed measurement techniques was the precision. It is influenced by the sensitivity and the background noise and affects the instrumental limits of detection, and eventually the limit of quantification of the analysis method and the final uncertainty of the measurement. The precision was estimated in terms of the RSDs obtained by injecting standard solutions repeatedly ($n = 5$) and the results obtained by the different evaluated instruments are shown in Figure 1. RSDs were in the same range for GC-ICP-MS and GC-NCI-MS even though GC-ICP-MS shows twice as much sensitivity than GC-NCI-MS. This can be explained taking into account the low backgrounds achieved due to the high selectivity provided by the NCI source towards strong electrophores when working in electron capture mode [32]. As can be observed, the RSDs provided by both techniques did not depend on the degree of bromination of the target analytes and concentration levels above $0.5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in the injected solution provide RSDs of 5% or below. The GC-EI-MS/MS showed overall higher RSDs, especially for the higher brominated congeners. This is due to the lower sensitivity provided by this technique in comparison with GC-NCI-MS and GC-ICP-MS, which could require higher enrichment factors to achieve the requirements of the WFD.

Instrumental limits of detection (ILODs)

Finally, the three techniques were compared in terms of absolute ILODs, which are influenced by the sensitivity, the precision achieved in the measurements and the injected volume. Resorting to instrumental techniques able to provide low ILODs it may be possible to improve the LOQs of the developed quantification methodologies. The ILODs obtained for the three studied instrumental setups are shown in Table 2, expressed as the lowest concentration level detected, calculated from the calibration curve plus three times its standard deviation. Again GC-ICP-MS and GC-NCI-MS provided similar results. ILODs were in the same range for all the priority congeners and for both studied m/z , although the values obtained for GC-ICP-MS were slightly better. Considering that LOQs are typically calculated as three times the LOD values, enrichment factors above 1500 and 2500 would be necessary to achieve quantifiable concentrations of PBDEs in the sample extracts when using GC-ICP-MS and GC-NCI-MS respectively. GC-EI-MS/MS showed higher ILODs

especially for the higher brominated congeners as can be presumed from the results obtained in the sensitivity and precision evaluations. Therefore, this technique will require higher enrichment factors, above 9000, or the injection of higher sample extract volumes than GC-ICP-MS and GC-NCI-MS in order to compensate for the lower ILODs for the priority PBDEs.

Determination of PBDEs in water samples in compliance with the WFD

Considering the instrumental capabilities shown in the previous section, the three MS systems could be potential candidates for the development of analytical methods able to meet the requirements of the WFD for the determination of PBDEs in water samples if the appropriate enrichment factors are achieved. The sample preparation procedure described in the experimental section involves the preconcentration of 1 L water sample to a final volume of around 100 μL , which would provide a theoretical enrichment factor of 10000 and therefore make feasible the quantification of PBDEs by the three proposed MS techniques. However, the achievement of these enrichment factors must be experimentally verified for real water matrices. The use of ^{81}Br labelled PBDEs under the optimized working conditions summarized in Table S2 and Table S3 served as a basis for the development of a sensitive IDMS quantification method for PBDEs using GC-ICP-MS and GC-NCI-MS. $^{13}\text{C}_{12}$ labelled PBDEs were used as spike for the development of an organic IDMS quantification method when using GC-EI-MS/MS as a detector under the optimised working conditions shown in Table S4.

The European legislation states that analytical methods that are to be applied to the determination of priority substances must provide a LOQ equal or below a value of 30% of the relevant EQS [12], meaning 0.15 ng L^{-1} or lower for PBDEs. The methodological LOQs were estimated for the three proposed methodologies by analysing ten replicate mineral water blank samples after spiking them with either with ^{81}Br or ^{13}C labelled PBDEs depending on the selected MS detection system. The obtained LOQs, expressed as ten times the standard deviation of ten replicate mineral water blanks, are summarised in Table 3. The three MS detection systems provided methodological LOQs below 0.15 ng L^{-1} for the six priority congeners. Despite showing higher ILODs, GC-EI-MS/MS provided methodological LOQs in the same range as GC-ICP-MS and GC-NCI-MS due to the high enrichment factors achieved by the proposed sample preparation method. The similar results obtained for the three methodologies indicate that following the proposed sample preparation procedure the LOQ values depend more on the variability between blank samples than on the instrumental capabilities.

The three proposed analytical methods were applied to the determination of priority PBDEs in a river water sample. The samples were treated as described in the experimental section. A set of three replicate samples were spiked with ^{81}Br -PBDEs and then measured by GC-ICP-MS and GC-NCI-MS and another set of three replicates were spiked with ^{13}C -PBDEs to be measured by GC-

EI-MS/MS. The concentration levels of the six priority congeners were in all samples below the methodological LOQs obtained for mineral water samples and therefore, these river water samples were considered as blanks for the determination of the LOQs of the different proposed methods when applied to the determination of PBDEs in whole water samples. The LOQs (Table 4) were calculated as 10 times the standard deviation of three river water samples analysed separately. The three studied MS techniques would be an appropriate candidate, in terms of LOQs, for the determination of PBDEs according to the WFD.

A second requirement for analytical methods to be considered suitable for the determination of priority substances in compliance with European regulation is that the estimated expanded uncertainties of measurements ($k = 2$) must be equal or below 50% at the level of the relevant EQS. The expanded uncertainties together with the recoveries were estimated for the river water sample matrix spiked with native PBDEs at a concentration level of ca. 0.25 ng L^{-1} for each priority congener and the appropriate amount of ^{81}Br or ^{13}C labelled analogue depending on the selected ionisation source. The six priority PBDEs were quantified by IDMS according to the equations described in the electronic supplementary material and the results, expressed in terms of recoveries are included in Table S5; **Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**, as well as the expanded uncertainties, calculated for each single sample replicate by using the GUM uncertainty calculation software (GUM Workbench 2.4, Metrodata GmbH, Weil am Rhein, Germany). The average recoveries obtained for the six priority congeners from the three replicate samples were in the range 79-97% for GC-ICP-MS, 67-100% for GC-NCI-MS and 90-106% for GC-EI-MS/MS. The three evaluated techniques provided acceptable results considering the very low concentration levels to be determined. The variability between the three replicates were lower than 7.5, 5 and 4.5 (%RSD) respectively, which indicates that good precisions were achieved in both the sample preparation method and the measurement procedures. The values obtained for each single congener by the three different techniques are compared in Figure 2. As can be observed the average recoveries were in very good agreement for the two sets of samples spiked with ^{81}Br -labelled congeners except for BDE 100 and 154. These two labelled congeners have a lower isotope enrichment which is known to give less precisions and higher uncertainties and may eventually lead to biased results, since this behaviour has not been observed when using ^{81}Br labelled spikes with higher isotope enrichment in combination with GC-NCI-MS detection [15]. The slightly different recoveries achieved when using ^{81}Br or ^{13}C labelled spikes can be explained considering that the natural standards used for the spiking of the river water samples were also used for the construction of the calibration curve in the GC-EI-MS/MS quantification method, whereas the ^{81}Br labelled spikes used for the quantification of PBDEs by GC-ICP-MS and GC-NCI-MS were characterised using a certified reference material. The uncertainties achieved by the three proposed quantification methods are below 50% for the six priority congeners at the studied concentration level (Table S5) and therefore the three of them are feasible for the determination of PBDEs in water samples

according to the requirements of the European legislation. The quantification method based in GC-ICP-MS provided the lowest expanded uncertainties followed by GC-NCI-MS and GC-EI-MS/MS showed the highest values. The contribution of the various uncertainty sources to the total expanded uncertainty was evaluated for the three proposed determination methods on each sample replicate. The concentration of the spikes and, to a lower extent, the isotope ratio measured in the blend sample-spike were the main sources of uncertainty in the GC-ICP-MS method (Figure S1). The uncertainty in the spike concentration is mainly due to the uncertainty in the concentration of the reference material used for the characterisation of the spike and therefore it cannot be lowered. The uncertainty in the isotope ratio of the blend could be lowered by increasing the precision in the experimental isotope ratio measurements. BDEs 100 and 154 showed also a significant contribution from the isotope ratio in the spike, which could be decreased by using spikes with higher isotope enrichment if they were available. The contribution of the main uncertainty sources for the GC-NCI-MS showed the same profile as the GC-ICP-MS, but with a higher contribution from isotope ratio in the blend, due to the experimental measurements, in this case (Figure S2). The quantification of PBDEs by GC-EI-MS/MS using ^{13}C labelled PBDEs as internal standards requires the construction of a calibration curve using natural standards. Since the equation used for the calculation of the concentration of the analytes in the water samples is different from the equation used for ^{81}Br labelled PBDEs, different parameters will contribute to the final expanded uncertainties (Figure S3), being the intercept and the slope of the calibration curve the main contributions for the six target analytes. These two parameters depend on the experimental measurements and therefore lower uncertainty values could be achieved by improving the precision in the measurements. The concentration of the labelled spikes, whose uncertainty cannot be experimentally improved as it is obtained from the certificate of analysis of the provider, affected also the total expanded uncertainty although to a lower extent. According to these results an improvement in the precision of the experimental measurements could help to decrease the expanded uncertainty of the GC-EI-MS/MS determination method whereas for the GC-ICP-MS and GC-NCI-MS methods the use of standards with lower associated expanded uncertainties would provide the main improvement to the total expanded uncertainty.

As already mentioned, the three proposed determination methods are appropriate for the determination of PBDEs according to the requirements of the WFD for a river water sample spiked with a solution containing the six priority congeners. However, as PBDEs are highly hydrophobic compounds, when they are present in real water samples they are typically bound to SPM. In this case the extraction of the target analytes and the equilibration with the spikes added as a solution can be incomplete and consequently the results could be inaccurate. In order to confirm the good performance of the different proposed methods under these conditions a mineral water sample free of PBDEs was spiked with a model SPM obtained from a milled sediment material containing a known amount of the priority congeners [27]. The concentration levels were in the range of the EQS

for BDEs 100, 153 and 154, 20 times lower for BDE 28, and 5 and 10 times higher for BDEs 47 and 99 respectively (Table S5). A set of three replicate samples spiked with SPM were analysed following each of the proposed methodologies and the obtained results are summarised in Table 5. together with the expanded uncertainties. The average recoveries obtained for the three evaluated methodologies are compared in Figure 3. The recoveries were in very good agreement for those analytes showing higher concentration levels, such as BDEs 47 and 99, with expanded uncertainties below 6% for GC-ICP-MS and GC-NCI-MS and below 9% for GC-EI-MS/MS. For those BDEs with concentration levels close to the EQS value (100, 153 and 154) the recoveries were very similar for GC-ICP-MS and GC-EI-MS/MS. GC-NCI-MS showed lower recoveries for BDEs 100 and 154. This effect had been observed for the river water samples spiked with a solution containing native PBDEs as well. BDE 153 showed expanded uncertainties below 4% for the GC-ICP-MS and GC-NCI-MS methods and below 30% for GC-EI-MS/MS. This can be explained considering that when using GC-EI-MS/MS the precision in the experimental measurements greatly decrease for the higher brominated congeners due to the lower instrumental sensitivity for these congeners (Figure 1). For BDEs 100 and 154 the expanded uncertainties are higher (15-20%) when using GC-ICP-MS and GC-NCI-MS due to the lower enrichment of the ⁸¹Br labelled analogues. When using GC-EI-MS/MS the uncertainties increase up to 18 and 40% respectively due to the poor sensitivity achieved for these congeners. BDE 28 showed changing recoveries and higher expanded uncertainties than expected as its concentration in the mineral water sample is ten times lower than the EQS and very close to the methodological LOQs especially for the GC-EI-MS/MS method. A detailed overview of the main sources of uncertainty affecting the total expanded uncertainty in the determination of PBDEs in a mineral water sample spiked with a model SPM can be found in the supplementary material (Figure S4, Figure S5 and Figure S6). In comparison with the river water samples spiked with a standard solution containing PBDEs the experimental measurements show overall a higher contribution to the final expanded uncertainty probably due to the higher complexity of this matrix for the three proposed methodologies.

Conclusions

For the first time three different analytical methods based on the liquid-liquid extraction of whole water samples, measurement of the extracts by GC-NCI-MS, GC-EI-MS/MS or GC-ICP-MS and quantification by IDMS using ⁸¹Br-labelled or ¹³C-labelled PBDEs spikes, depending on the selected ionization source were developed and compared for the determination of the named priority PBDEs in whole water samples. The three proposed methodologies met the requirements of the European legislation in terms of LOQs and expanded uncertainties ($k = 2$). The accuracies, expressed in terms of recoveries were between 70 and 110% in all cases for the three proposed determination methods. The results obtained by the different quantification methods, based on different MS ionisation techniques, were in good agreement, ruling out the presence of interfering substances

that may affect the final results even for complex matrices like the mineral water containing model SPM.

GC-ICP-MS provided the highest sensitivity and the lowest ILODs. The determination method based in this technique showed the lowest expanded uncertainties, with the main contribution from the standard solutions used for the quantification. GC-NCI-MS provided lower sensitivity than GC-ICP-MS but the ILODs were in the same range due to the low backgrounds. The uncertainties were slightly higher and the LOQs were in the same range as for GC-ICP-MS, so it can be considered a good alternative. However, this method showed some accuracy problems for PBDEs 100 and 154 in complex matrices with much lower recoveries than those achieved for the other two studied techniques which might be attributable to the lower enrichment of the ⁸¹Br labelled spikes used for the IDMS quantification. GC-EI-MS/MS showed the lowest sensitivity, especially for the higher brominated congeners, which leads to increased ILODs. The use of a sample preparation method with a high pre-concentration factor compensated for the lower ILODs providing appropriate LOQs to meet the European legislation. The expanded uncertainties were higher, especially for the higher brominated congeners, but still within the range allowed by the WFD. The uncertainty associated with the experimental measurements played a more important role in the quantification of PBDEs by GC-EI-MS/MS due to the lower sensitivities and precisions provided by this technique.

Acknowledgments

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union on the basis of Decision No 912/2009/EC within the context of an EMRP Research Grant, which was part of the EURAMET JRP ENV08 -Traceable measurements for monitoring critical pollutants under the European Water Framework Directive (WFD-2000/60/EC). The EMRP is jointly funded by the EMRP participating countries within EURAMET and the European Union.

The authors would also like to acknowledge Peter Planitz and Bernhard Rothweiler from Agilent Technologies (Waldbronn, Germany) for the help and the possibility to use the GC-MS/MS at the Agilent application lab.

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Table 1. Sensitivity factor (counts · min · g / pg) showed by the different studied techniques for the detection of PBDEs

Congeners	GC-ICP-MS		GC-NCI-MS		GC-EI-MS/MS
	m/z = 79	m/z = 81	m/z = 79	m/z = 81	SRM (Table S4)
BDE28	10.2	9.9	5.2	5.2	6.6
BDE47	11.5	11.3	4.9	4.7	2.5
BDE99	11.5	11.3	5.9	5.8	1.9
BDE100	11.9	11.6	4.9	5.0	3.0
BDE153	11.4	11.2	5.8	6.0	0.9
BDE154	11.9	11.6	6.2	6.1	1.4

Table 2. Instrumental limits of detection (fg)

Congeners	GC-ICP-MS		GC-NCI-MS		GC-EI-MS/MS
	m/z = 79	m/z = 81	m/z = 79	m/z = 81	SRM (Table S4)
BDE28	62	81	78	81	150
BDE47	52	65	71	47	220
BDE99	70	54	65	61	320
BDE100	57	56	65	90	270
BDE153	67	72	70	100	460
BDE154	66	73	130	140	290

Table 3. Methodological limits of quantification (ng L⁻¹) obtained for the three quantification methods

Congeners	GC-ICP-MS	GC-NCI-MS	GC-EI-MS/MS
BDE28	0.013	0.0023	0.024
BDE47	0.059	0.049	0.097
BDE99	0.035	0.015	0.027
BDE100	0.019	0.068	0.014
BDE153	0.0057	0.0083	0.0071
BDE154	0.019	0.057	0.051
ΣPBDEs	0.15	0.20	0.22

Table 4. Limits of quantification (ng L⁻¹) obtained for the three quantification methods in river water samples

Congeners	GC-ICP-MS	GC-NCI-MS	GC-EI-MS/MS
BDE28	0.024	0.022	0.0040
BDE47	0.061	0.085	0.2319
BDE99	0.014	0.0075	0.0221
BDE100	0.011	0.032	0.0063
BDE153	0.028	0.014	0.0014
BDE154	0.021	0.020	0.0003
ΣPBDEs	0.16	0.18	0.27

Table 5. Concentrations of PBDEs with their standard deviations (ng L⁻¹) and expanded uncertainties (k = 2) in a mineral water sample spiked with a model SPM

GC-ICP-MS						
	Replicate 1		Replicate 2		Replicate 3	
	Concentration	U (%)	Concentration	U (%)	Concentration	U (%)
BDE 28	0.028 ± 0.004	11	0.030 ± 0.004	12	0.035 ± 0.004	10
BDE 47	2.2 ± 0.2	6	2.2 ± 0.2	6	2.2 ± 0.2	6
BDE 99	5.2 ± 0.3	4	5.3 ± 0.3	6	5.3 ± 0.3	6
BDE 100	0.9 ± 0.2	13	0.8 ± 0.2	15	0.8 ± 0.2	16
BDE 153	1.14 ± 0.04	4	1.05 ± 0.04	4	1.01 ± 0.04	4
BDE 154	0.59 ± 0.06	9	0.61 ± 0.07	10	0.57 ± 0.07	12
GC-NCI-MS						
	Replicate 1		Replicate 2		Replicate 3	
	Concentration	U (%)	Concentration	U (%)	Concentration	U (%)
BDE 28	0.018 ± 0.004	18	0.014 ± 0.005	31	0.021 ± 0.005	20
BDE 47	2.0 ± 0.2	6	2.2 ± 0.2	6	2.3 ± 0.2	6
BDE 99	5.0 ± 0.2	4	5.1 ± 0.3	5	5.1 ± 0.3	4.5
BDE 100	0.6 ± 0.1	18	0.57 ± 0.10	17	0.59 ± 0.10	17
BDE 153	1.12 ± 0.04	3	1.18 ± 0.05	4	1.11 ± 0.04	3.6
BDE 154	0.17 ± 0.04	23	0.22 ± 0.04	16	0.188 ± 0.04	18
GC-EI-MS/MS						
	Replicate 1		Replicate 2		Replicate 3	
	Concentration	U (%)	Concentration	U (%)	Concentration	U (%)
BDE 28	0.0 ± 0.1	280	0.0 ± 0.1	270	0.0 ± 0.1	380
BDE 47	2.4 ± 0.2	8	2.3 ± 0.2	8	2.3 ± 0.2	8
BDE 99	5.3 ± 0.5	9	5.2 ± 0.5	9	5.4 ± 0.5	9
BDE 100	0.9 ± 0.2	16	0.9 ± 0.2	17	0.9 ± 0.2	18
BDE 153	1.3 ± 0.4	30	1.2 ± 0.3	25	1.2 ± 0.3	23
BDE 154	0.5 ± 0.3	40	0.6 ± 0.3	40	0.5 ± 0.3	41

Figure 1. Precision obtained by the different instrumental systems.

Figure 2. Comparison of the recoveries obtained by different quantification methods in the determination of PBDEs in a river water sample. Error bars represent standard deviations obtained from three replicate samples analysed separately.

Figure 3. Comparison of the recoveries obtained by different quantification methods in the determination of PBDEs in a mineral water sample spiked with model SPM. Error bars represent standard deviations obtained from three replicate samples analysed separately.

